

Assessment of oral Health status and oral hygiene practices of school children studying in selected schools of the city.

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ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION: India, a developing country, faces many challenges in rendering oral health needs. Most of the Indian population resides in rural areas. It is necessary to know the prevalence and distribution of oral health problems and understand the dental health practices that people follow. Such information is basic for formulation of oral health policies and appropriate programs. The appropriate policies and programs will facilitate in improving awareness and knowledge of the general public about the preventive and promotive aspects of oral health as well as, to create the required services and train the necessary dental manpower to meet these needs. Lack of awareness about dental diseases has resulted in gross neglect of oral health.

METHOD: The research approach adopted for the present research is Quantitative Descriptive Research Approach because the study aimed to assess the oral health status and hygiene practices of school children studying in selected schools of the city. The population of children between 12-14 years. The research design was selected for present study Non-experimental descriptive **research** The data is piece of information or facts that are collected in a research study. An idea data collection procedure is one that captures a data in a way that is relevant, credible, accurate, truthful, and sensitive, the most important and crucial aspect of any research is data collection, which gives an answer to the questions included under study.

The present study was Aimed to assess the oral health status and hygiene practices of school children studying in selected schools of the city.

Assessment of oral health status of school children and oral hygiene practices of school children

Association of study finding with selected demographic variable. Hypothesis testing was done by using chi-square test.

Results: The oral health status of the study population using WHO 1997 oral health assessment form revealed that 1 (1%) had oral mucosal lesions, 3 (3%) had enamel opacities/hypoplasia, 8(8%) had dental fluorosis, 10(10%) were suffering from periodontal health problem, 58 (58%) were suffering from dental caries. The Dental Aesthetics Index, recommended by the WHO was used to report malocclusion. There were only 2% of subjects who had malocclusion.

CONCLUSION: Conclusion of the study overall it can be said that the result relating to oral hygiene practices and knowledge were good but only 31% of the students visited the dentist and the concept of regular dental check-up was almost nil. Hence the need for continuing dental education through promotion is emphasized with justification.

KEYWORDS: Oral health

INTRODUCTION: India, a developing country, faces many challenges in rendering oral health needs. Most of the Indian population resides in rural areas. It is necessary to know the prevalence and distribution of oral health problems and understand the dental health practices that people follow. Such information is basic for formulation of oral health policies and appropriate programs. The appropriate policies and programs will facilitate in improving awareness and knowledge of the general public about the preventive and promotive aspects of oral health as well as, to create the required services and train the necessary dental manpower to meet these needs. Lack of awareness about dental diseases has resulted in gross neglect of oral health.

India does not have a national oral health policy at present, though a national health policy has been drafted. This suggests that the policy makers are neglectful of oral health, and its promotion is not being given the necessary attention in our country. Policy makers must be made aware that oral health is fundamental to general health and well-being.

Oral health is integral to general health; nobody cannot be healthy without oral health. Many general diseases manifest in the mouth, and oral disease may be the first indication of other life-threatening disease.

Maintenance of adequate oral health depends on the adoption of specific behaviours, namely dental check-ups, toothbrushing frequency, diet and sugar consumption, dental floss use, and other methods of interproximal cleaning.

These behaviours play an essential role in the prevention of dental caries and periodontal disease since adequate oral hygiene habits and regular use of dental services have shown effectiveness in reducing the prevalence of these diseases as in the prevention and early diagnosis of oral diseases.

Adolescents, like the general population, behave not only by their own choices and motivations, experience, lifestyle, beliefs, and value system but also are conditioned by sociocultural norms and by the oral health system that may differ between countries, with immediate or future impairment in oral health. Oral health attitudes acquired at this stage of existence are fundamental to maintaining good oral health habits throughout the life.

Oral diseases have psychological, physical, and social consequences on adolescents' lives. Oral health perception is linked to the valorisation of this concept and plays an essential role in the concept of body image and quality of life. The fact that adolescents can consider oral health as a low priority in health care and can affect the development of health behaviours and the ability to obtain knowledge that promotes good oral health.

There is evidence that supports the fact that proper oral health knowledge presents better oral care practices. Alongside this, a positive attitude toward oral health practices encourages better oral health habits. An improved understanding of what adolescents currently know about oral

health can guide the development and implementation of oral health educational strategies to ensure that the additional knowledge translates into improved oral health.

Health is the most common theme in various cultures. It is a fundamental human right irrespective of any caste, creed, religion, political beliefs, and economic or social conditions. Oral health is fundamental to general health and well-being. A healthy mouth enables a person to eat, speak, and socialize without having any disease which is in active form or causes any type of embarrassment and discomfort.

Oral diseases are the major public health issues depending on their incidence and prevalence. However, oral health knowledge is a prerequisite for health-related behaviors.

Oral health is one of the key indicators of overall health, well-being, and quality of life of an individual. It not only affects people physically and psychologically but also influences how they grow, look, speak, chew, taste food, and socialize in their community. It is sad on our part that dental health has been neglected over the years, especially in the underprivileged areas. As per the World Health Organization, it is “a state of being free from chronic mouth and facial pain, oral and throat cancer, oral sores, birth defects such as cleft lip and palate, periodontal (gum) disease, tooth decay and tooth loss and other diseases and disorders that limit an individual’s capacity in biting, chewing, smiling and psychological well-being.”

Worldwide, 60–90% of schoolchildren and nearly 100% of adults have oral problems. Dental diseases are preventable to a larger extent. However, information and awareness about the preventive aspects of oral and dental health are usually not applied in day-to-day practice.

METHOD:

Study Design: The research design was selected for present study Non-experimental descriptive research design.

Setting: The present study was conducted in the specific place where the data collection occurs. The study was conducted in selected schools of the city.

Sampling Technique: sampling technique used is non-probability purposive sampling technique

Population: The population for the study will be High school children

Data Collection:

Method of data collection:

- 1) The investigator introduced herself and himself and explained the purpose of the study to the head of the department.
- 2) The study was explained to the school children and informed consent was taken to participate in the study.
- 3) In this study all the available samples, who were meeting the exclusion and inclusion criteria were included.
- 4) First explained objectives to the all subjects and daily data was collected from available samples till data collection period.

ORGANIZATION OF THE DATA:

Section I: Description of Sociodemographic data of students

Section II: Assessment of oral health status of school children and oral hygiene practices of school children

Section III: Hypotheses testing

Association of study finding with selected demographic variable. Hypothesis testing was done by using chi-square test.

Analysis and interpretation of the data

Analysis is a process of organizing and synthesizing data in such a way that research questions can be answered, and hypothesis tested. This chapter deals with the analysis and interpretation, result of the data collected from 100 samples through a non-experimental descriptive research design. Non probability purposive samplings technique was used for selection of school students with the objective of assessing the oral Health status and oral hygiene practices of school children studying in selected schools of the city. The collected data was tabulated in master sheet and analysed by using descriptive and inferential statistics as per the objectives of the study.

Section I: Description of Sociodemographic data of students

Section II: Assessment of oral health status of school children and oral hygiene practices of school children

Section III: Hypotheses testing

Association of study finding with selected demographic variable. Hypothesis testing was done by using chi-square test.

Section – I: Description of Sociodemographic data (n=100)

Table No: I

SN	Variable	Frequency	%
1	Age in years		
a	12	38	38
b	13	40	40
c	14	14	14
d	15	08	08
2	Gender		
a	Male	37	37
b	Female	63	63
c	Transgender	00	00
3	Religion		
a	Hindu	78	48
b	Muslim	02	02
c	Christian	15	15
d	Buddhist	05	05
e	Others	00	00
4	Area of Residence		
a	Hostel	00	00
b	Home	100	100

5	Type of School		
a	Government aided Private Schools	20	20
b	Private Schools	50	50
c	International Schools	30	30

The above-mentioned table deals with the demographic data of sample regarding age, Gender, religion, Area of Residence and type of school.

Fig no: 1

Pie diagram showing percentage wise distribution according to the Age of the respondents

Percentage wise distribution of respondents according to their Age depicts that highest percentage (40%) of respondents were in the age group of 14 years followed by 38 % of the respondents were in the age group of 12 years, 14% of the respondents were in the age group of 14 years and 8% of the respondents were in the age group of 15 years and above. **Hence, it can be interpreted that most of the respondents were in the age group of 13 years.**

Fig no: 2

Bar diagram showing percentage wise distribution according to the Gender of the respondents

Percentage wise distribution of respondents according to their gender depicts that highest percentage (63%) of respondents were female and (37%) of the respondents were male. **Hence, it can be interpreted that most of the respondents were female.**

Fig no: 3

Pie diagram showing percentage wise distribution according to the religion of the respondents

Percentage wise distribution of respondents according to their religion depicts that highest percentage (78%) of respondents were Hindu, 15% of the respondents were Christian, 5% of the respondents were Buddhist and 2% of the respondents were Muslim. **Hence, it can be interpreted that most of the respondents were Hindu.**

Fig no: 4

Bar diagram showing percentage wise distribution according to the type of residence
Percentage wise distribution of respondents according to their type of residence depicts that highest percentage all (100%) of respondents type of residence was home.

Fig no: 5
Pie diagram showing percentage wise distribution according to the type of school of the respondents

Percentage wise distribution of respondents according to their type of schools depicts that highest percentage (50%) of respondent’s were from private schools and 30% of respondents were from international school. It can be interpreted that most of the respondents were from private schools.

Section II: Assessment of oral health status of school children and oral hygiene practices of school children.

Table 2: Distribution of the study subjects according to oral health status

SN	Parameter	Present		Absent	
		Frequency	%	Frequency	%
1	Clinical Assessment (extra oral)	00	00	100	100
2	TMJ-Symptoms	00	00	100	100
3	TMJ-Signs	00	00	100	100
4	Oral Mucosa	01	01	99	99
5	Enamel Opacities/Hypoplasia	03	03	97	97
6	Dental Fluorosis	08	08	92	92
7	Calculus and Gingival diseases	10	10	90	90
8	Dentition Status	58	58	42	42
9	Treatment Needs	58	58	42	42
10	Prosthetic Need	00	00	100	100
11	Malocclusion	02	02	98	98

Fig no: 6

Bar diagram showing percentage wise Distribution of the study subjects according to oral health status

The oral health status of the study population using WHO 1997 oral health assessment form revealed that 1 (1%) had oral mucosal lesions, 3 (3%) had enamel opacities/hypoplasia, 8(8%) had dental fluorosis, 10(10%) were suffering from periodontal health problem, 58 (58%) were suffering from dental caries. The Dental Aesthetics Index, recommended by the WHO was used to report malocclusion. There were only 2% of subjects who had malocclusion.

Table 3: Assessment of the study subjects according to oral health practices

SN	Question on practice	Options	Frequency	Percentage
1	What do you use for cleaning your teeth	Dental floss only	00	00
		Brush & Tooth paste only	72	72
		Brush & Tooth paste with dental floss *	28	28
		Do not know	00	00
2	How often do you brush your teeth each day?	Less than once a day	02	02
		Once a day	38	38
		Twice a day*	50	50
		More than twice a day	10	10
3	How much toothpaste do you normally put on your toothbrush?	Full length of bristles	40	40
		Half-length of bristles	25	25
		About the size of a pea*	20	20
		About the size of a grain of rice	15	15
4	How long do you normally take to brush your teeth?	About 30 seconds	02	02
		About 1 minute	30	30
		About 2 minutes*	50	50
		Do not know	18	18
5	When do you normally brush your teeth?	Only in the morning	40	40
		Only in the evening	00	00
		In the morning and evening*	58	58
		Do not know	02	02
6	How often do you floss your teeth each day?	Never	60	60
		Once a day*	20	20
		Twice or more than twice a day	10	10
		Do not know	10	10
7	How often do you visit your dentist?	Once a year	15	15
		Twice a year*	15	15
		Only when I have a toothache	50	50
		I do not visit the dentist	20	20

Fig no: 7
Bar diagram showing percentage wise distribution of respondents according to the oral health practices: What do you use for cleaning your teeth

Fig no: 8
Bar diagram showing percentage wise distribution of respondents according to the oral health practices: How often do you brush your teeth each day?

Fig no: 9
Bar diagram showing percentage wise distribution of respondents according to the oral health practices: How much toothpaste do you normally put on your toothbrush?

Fig no: 10

Bar diagram showing percentage wise distribution of respondents according to the oral health practices: How long do you normally take to brush your teeth?

Fig no: 11

Bar diagram showing percentage wise distribution of respondents according to the oral health practices: When do you normally brush your teeth?

Fig no: 12

Bar diagram showing percentage wise distribution of respondents according to the oral health practices: How often do you floss your teeth each day?

Fig no: 13

Bar diagram showing percentage wise distribution of respondents according to the oral health practices: How often do you visit your dentist?

Section III

Association of study findings with selected demographic variable.

Table 4

Association of Oral health status with selected demographic variable.

SN	Variable	P value	Level of Significance
1	Age	0.126	Not Significant
a	12 years		
b	13 years		
c	14 years		
d	15 years		
2	Gender	0.001	Significant
a	Male		
b	Female		
3	Religion	0.72	Not Significant
a	Hindu		
b	Muslim		
c	Christian		
d	Buddhist		
4	Type of School	0.001	Significant
a	Government aided Private Schools		
b	Private Schools		
c	International Schools		

p ≥ 0.05, not significant

Chi square values were calculated to find out the association between the Oral health status with selected demographic variables. Significant association was found between the Oral health status with gender and type of school as the p value is less than 0.05 level of significance.

Table 5

Association of Oral health practices with selected demographic variable.

SN	Variable	P value	Level of Significance
1	Age	1.21	Not Significant
a	12 years		
b	13 years		
c	14 years		
2	Gender	2.32	Not Significant
a	Male		
b	Female		
3	Religion	1.11	Not Significant
a	Hindu		
b	Muslim		
c	Christian		
4	Type of School	0.001	Significant
a	Government aided Private Schools		
b	Private Schools		
c	International Schools		

p ≥ 0.05, not significant

Chi square values were calculated to find out the association between the Oral health practices with selected demographic variables. Significant association was found between the Oral health practices and type of school as the p value is less than 0.05 level of significance.

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